

CAA Netherland-Flanders National Chapter Information and Report

National Chapter*: Netherland-Flanders

Submitted by*: Ronald Visser, Devi Taelman, Alex Brandsen and Alicia Walsh

Date Submitted*: 1 September 2025

Chapter Organisational Details

Chapter Leadership

Term Dates for the Current Steering Committee:

Name*	Chapter Position*	Email Address
Ronald Visser	Chair	r.m.visser@saxion.nl
Devi Taelman	Treasurer	devi.taelman@vub.be
Alex Brandsen	Communications officer	a.brandsen@arch.leidenuniv.nl
Alicia Walsh	Secretary	a.s.c.walsh@arch.leidenuniv.nl

CAA Steering Committee Representative*: Ronald Visser

This is often the chair, but any member of the chapter's leadership can be designated as the Steering Committee representative. However, the Steering Committee representative **must be a member of CAA International** while serving in this capacity.

Chapter Membership

Total Number of Current Members: 183

If you have different categories membership categories for Full Members, Students, and/or Low Income Members, please provide the numbers of members at each level:

Membership Level	Number of Members
No levels, because membership is free	183

Chapter Contact Information

Chapter Website*: <https://nfl.caa-international.org/>

Chapter Social Media Channel(s) (optional):

Platform*	Handle*
Twitter (X)	https://twitter.com/caanfl (not in use)
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/caanfl/
Instagram	-
LinkedIn	-
YouTube	-
Mastodon	https://akademienl.social/@caanfl

General Contact Email for the Chapter*:

info@caanfl.nl

Chapter Description

Brief Description of Your Chapter*:

CAA Netherlands – Flanders (CAA-NL-FL) represents the Dutch and Flemish national chapter of the international CAA. Its main aim is to bring together archaeologists, mathematicians and computer scientists based in the Netherlands and Flanders, thus encouraging communication between these disciplines and giving an overview of current work in the field. Through yearly meetings, CAA-NL-FL wishes to stimulate discussion and future progress.

CAA-NL was founded on 26 September 1996 and became CAA-NL-FL in 2010 as a joint chapter for the Netherlands and Flanders, because we share the same language. It has been a growing community ever since. We organize an annual Chapter Meeting, and every two years this takes the form of a joint event with our German colleagues (CAA-DE). Our goal is to provide a platform that welcomes both established and early career researchers to present their work and engage in dialogue.

The organisation is currently administered by four speakers: Ronald Visser, Alicia Walsh, Devi Taelman, and Alex Brandsen. Membership of CAA-NL-FL is free and open to all. Anyone attending a meeting of CAA-NL-FL automatically becomes a member.

Report for the CAA National Chapter of Netherlands-Flanders

Reporting Period*: 2024

Netherland-Flanders

Submitted by*: Ronald Visser, Devi Taelman, Alex Brandsen and Alicia Walsh

Date Submitted*: : Update on the National Chapter Activities:*

In 2024, we organized our Joint Chapter Meeting with CAA Germany AG. The event took place in Groningen on October 24 and 25 and was hosted by the Archaeological Institute of the University of Groningen. The subjects of the various lectures were diverse, reflecting the diversity of topics and people within our Chapter. The presentations resulted in interesting discussions. We also welcomed some new members into our community, and laid the foundation for new collaborations and friendships. Overall, the two-day meeting was a success.

The full programme can be found below. Abstracts for the papers can be found in the last section on the website (<https://nlfl.caa-international.org/events/meetings/joint-chapter-meeting-2024/>).

Thursday 24 October

12:30 – 12:50 Registration

12:50 – 13:00 Welcome, introduction and practicalities

13:00 – 15:00 3D Technologies

- Jitte Waagen – Virtual Past Places: VR for education, results of the SURF incentive scheme project at UvA
- Costas Papadopoulos & Alicia Walsh – Revisiting Scholarly Publication: Evaluation and Peer Review of 3D Scholarship

- Alexis Maldonado Ruiz – Digitisation and 3D Printing to improve accessibility of archaeological heritage for visually impaired people
- Lutz Schubert – Modelling the Maya Landscape

15:00 – 15:30 Coffee break

15:30 – 17:30 Open Science & Networks

- Ronald Visser – Developing the R package dendroNetwork for dendro-archaeology: lessons learned
- Bjørn Peare Bartholdy – RchaeoStats: Open, online teaching materials for learning statistics with R
- Dries Daems – Presenting NASSA: Network for Agent-Based Modelling of Socio-Ecological Systems in Archaeology
- Erik Kroon – Beyond Pots, Potters, and Peoples: Using Network Analysis, Probability Theory and Ceramic Chaînes Opératoires to Shed New Light on the Corded Ware Transition

18:00 Social dinner*

Friday 25 October

09:00 – 09:30 Registration

09:30 – 11:00 Remote Sensing & Predictive Modeling

- Agnes Schneider – From FAIR principles to FAIR practices in archaeological remote sensing: where are we?
- Simon Seyfried – Computing in Agricultural Remote Sensing for Aerial Archaeology
- Afke van Zijverden – Preserving Prehistory for the Future; Predictive modelling for protecting submerged and coastal Mesolithic sites.

11:00 – 11:30 Coffee break

11:30 – 13:00 Statistics & Databases

- Roderick Geerts – From Pottery to Patterns. Correspondence Analysis of large Roman period datasets
- Eduardo Herrera Malatesta – A Framework for Quantifying Uncertainties in Spatial Analysis
- Mark R. Groenhuijzen – Constructing the limes site database: building a cross-boundary site database to study border systems

13:00 – 14:00 Lunch Break*

14:00 – 15:30 Artificial Intelligence

- Karsten Lambers – Multimodal AI for the Analysis of Historical Maps
- Lieven Verdonck – Interactive, machine-learning based semantic segmentation of geophysical data
- Alex Brandsen – OpenAI vs. Open Source – Evaluating the Performance of Large Language Models on Extracting Radiocarbon Dates from Archaeology Papers

15:30 – 16:00 CAA-NL-FL Annual General Meeting, conclusions, and goodbye